

The effect of advertising, personal selling and sales promotion on purchase decision: A case of Padang cements brand in Medan, North Sumatra, Indonesia

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Abstract:

Marketing is a series of activities and processes of creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging valuable offerings for customers, clients, partners, and the public against the products offered. PT Semen Padang is a cement-based enterprise which has been established since 1910 and is also the oldest cement industry company in Indonesia. The company is supported by the level of product sales. One can be seen from the sales volume of the company. Company sales volume is largely dependent on customer purchasing decisions. Purchase decision is the action of a consumer to buy or not to purchase a product. Various factors can influence consumers in purchasing a product of goods or services, one of which is how a company is able to do its marketing activities. The formulation of the problem in this research is whether advertising, personal selling, and sales promotion affect purchasing decision of Semen Padang product in Medan city. This study aims to determine the influence of advertising, personal selling and sales promotion to the purchase decision of Semen Padang products in the city of Medan. This research is a type of hypothesis testing research with research population are consumers who have used Semen Padang products in Medan city. Sample selection is made by simple random sampling which is a technique to get a sample that is directly done on the sampling unit, which in this research selected 81 respondents. The data used are primary data and secondary data, qualitative and quantitative. This study analyzes the effect of advertising, personal selling and sales promotion on purchase decisions. The research method used is multiple regressions model. The empirical results of this study indicate that partially advertising has an insignificant effect on purchase decisions while personal selling and sales promotion have a significant effect on purchase decisions. However, simultaneously advertising, personal selling, and sales promotion have a significant effect on the purchase decision. Among the three independent variables, personal selling has the highest influence on the purchase decision of Semen Padang products in Medan.

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INTRODUCTION

PT Semen Padang is a cement-based enterprise which has been established since 1910 and is also the oldest cement industry company in Indonesia. PT Semen Padang is one of the leading companies in Indonesia. The advanced companies are supported by high sales rates, seen from the sales volume of the company. Company sales volume fluctuations depend on consumer purchasing decisions. Purchase decisions are the actions of consumers to buy or not to the product. Various factors affecting consumers in purchasing a product or service, one of which is how the company conducts its marketing activities. Marketing is an activity and process of creating, communicating, delivering, and redeeming offers that are valuable to customers, clients, partners, and the general public towards the product. Medan is one of the cities of Padang cement marketing area in Sumatra Island. Semen Padang handles national projects in Medan City, but cement industry competition is quite tight in Medan. Products offered include Portland Type I cement (OPC) and Portland Pozzolan cement (PPC) cement based on market demand in Medan and dominated by property and national projects. According to Kotler and Amstrong (2011) "Promotion mix or marketing communications mix. The specific blend of promotion tools that the company uses to communicate customer value and build customer relationships persuasively." It is a special combination of promotional tools that companies use to convince, communicate customer value and build customer relationships. The promotion strategy was conducted in Medan City in the face of tighter market competition. Like advertising support, promotion through radio, billboard, store brand board, sponsorship, personal selling is building brand equity with customers and sales promotion. Areas of activity managers and distributors to conduct field surveys, providing reward programs to distributors and building stores such as end customer reward programs. The activity encourages consumers to buy Padang cement products. Sales promotion is an activity every year to encourage the building store to increase the sales of Padang cement to consumers. Luis and Denny (2016) in their research show that promotional mix variables have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Andri (2015) shows that promotional mixes consisting of advertising, personal sales, sales promotions, and publicity simultaneously have a significant effect on consumer decisions while partial sales of personal and sales promotion have a significant effect but advertising and publicity have no significant effect on consumers' decision to buy. While Roni (2016) in his research that promotion mix has a significant effect on buying decisions simultaneously, while advertising, public relation and personal selling variables have no significant effect on purchasing decisions, sales promotion variable has a significant effect on purchase decision and direct marketing has a significant effect on the purchase decision.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Advertising

Advertising is an indirect communication paid and used by certain sponsors to convey to people about a product. According to Machfoedz (2010) that advertisements are all forms of informational presentation and indirect promotion sponsored to offer ideas, goods or services. Promotion or advertising activities have a specific purpose of persuading, influencing and informing and reminding customers of the company or the products or services they have.

Personal Selling

According to Kotler and Armstrong, (2012), personal selling is referred to "personal presentation by the firm's sales force to make sales and to build customer relationships." This

tactic is most effective during certain stages of the buying process, especially when trying to build up the buyer's preferences, convictions, and actions. Personal sales refer to "personal presentations by corporate salespeople to make sales and building relationships with customers." The tactics are most active during certain stages of the purchasing process, primarily building buyer preferences, beliefs, and actions that can affect consumers to buy products offered. According to Kotler and Keller (2012), six steps must be run by personal selling, namely: Prospecting and Qualifying: the first step to selling is identifying prospective customers. Selection of prospective customers by contacting them via message or telephone to find out the interest, buying interest and financial ability of prospective customers. Pre-Approach: salesperson phase looking for prospective customer information from the company about the needs of prospective clients, who has the role of deciding the purchase, and others. Presentation and Demonstration: salesperson phase tells about the product to the buyer by using feature approaches, advantages, benefits, and value. Overcoming Objections: the sales force phase addresses the problems faced by consumers who are blocking the purchase process. Divided two are psychological barriers (other brand preference, apathetic, pre-defined ideas, and more) and logical barriers (price, delivery time, and product or company characteristics). Closing: buyer phase performs real action, decision or input, and questions. Follow Up and Maintenance: to ensure customer satisfaction and repurchase. After closing, the salesperson must notify all requirements such as delivery time, purchase terms, and other matters that are important to the consumer.

Sales Promotion

Sales Promotion is a short-term promotional activity designed to stimulate consumers to buy or work with distributors, sales agents or other trading members. It is imperative because it can increase product sales. The sales promotion also comprises all incentives offered to customers and channel members to encourage the purchase of a product. Sales promotion consists of two forms of consumer promotion and trade promotion. "Sales promotions consist of all of the incentives offered to customers and channel members to encourage product purchases; Sales Promotion take two forms: consumer promotions and trade promotions. Consumer promotions are aimed at those who use the product or end users. They may be individuals or households. Another end user may be a word, and consumer promotions are offered in both consumer markets and business-to-business markets. "Clow and Baack (2012). According to (Griffin, 2007) there are several types of sales promotions as corporate promotion activities: Coupons are used to stimulate customers to try new products, keep customers from their competing products or persuade existing customers to buy competitor products or persuade existing customers to buy more. Point of Purchase (POP) is a display that makes it easy for customers to find products and make it easier for sellers to set aside their competitors from shopping considerations. Premium (gift) is a free product or discount, given to consumers when they buy certain products. Trade show allows the company to rent outlets to display and demonstrate products to customers with special attention or who are ready to buy. Customers, distributors and sales representatives can be encouraged to increase sales by using contests or sweepstakes.

Purchase Decision

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), consumer buying decisions are buying the most preferred brands of existing alternatives, but there are two factors between purchasing intentions and purchasing decisions. The first factor is the attitude of others and the second factor is the situational factor. The purchase preferences and intentions do not necessarily

lead to actual purchases. Sutisna and Sunyoto (2013), three critical aspects of understanding the consumer purchase decision model: the existence of a model, the view of consumer behavior can be in an integrated perspective. The consumer purchase decision model is the basis for developing an effective marketing strategy. The consumer purchase decision model for segmentation and positioning. Based on the theoretical basis, the hypothesis to be tested on the research is as follows:

H1: Advertising partially has a significant effect on purchase decisions.

H2: Personal Selling partially has a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

H3: Sales Promotion partially has a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research based on the method used is correlational research and data type used is quantitative research. Correlational research aims to detect the extent to which variations in a related factor or correlate between one factor and the other factors based on correlation coefficients. In this study, the sample size of 81 respondents is considered sufficient (representative) to represent the research population. Based on Sugiyono (2012) about the size of a decent sample of research is between 30 and 500. Therefore a sample size of 81 respondents is considered to represent the population.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Respondents Characteristics
Table 1: Respondents Characteristics

Descriptions		Amount	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	65	80,2
	Female	16	19,8
Age	21 - 30 years	32	39,5
	31 - 40 years	25	30,9
	> 48 years	24	29,6
Occupations	Entrepreneurs	22	27,2
	Private Employees	36	44,4
	Public Employees	11	13,6
	Construction Workers	11	13,6
	Other Work	1	1,2
Total		81	100,0

In table 1 presents the following: the majority of respondents are male by 65 respondents (80,2%). The respondents aged 21-30 years were the most respondents with 32 respondents (39.5%). Furthermore, the occupations of the majority of respondents are private employees at 36 respondents (44.4%).

Validity Test

With a total sample of 116 respondents, the correlation analysis was conducted between the questionnaire score and the validity value (r-critical). For the r product moment (r-critical), at 81 samples, with a significant level of 5% is 0.361, if the r-count value is higher or equal to

0.361, then it can be stated that the instrument is valid. The following table of validity test results of the research instrument is as follows:

**Table .1 Validity Test
Corrected Item-Total Correlation Variable**

Statement	R-count	R-table	Validity
Advertising (X11)	0,729	0,361	Valid
X12	0,640	0,361	Valid
X13	0,603	0,361	Valid
X14	0,596	0,361	Valid
X15	0,589	0,361	Valid
X16	0,647	0,361	Valid
X17	0,729	0,361	Valid
X18	0,702	0,361	Valid
Personal Selling (X2)			
X21	0,468	0,361	Valid
X22	0,577	0,361	Valid
X23	0,487	0,361	Valid
X24	0,384	0,361	Valid
X25	0,577	0,361	Valid
X26	0,458	0,361	Valid
Sales Promotion (X3)			
X31	0,646	0,361	Valid
X32	0,486	0,361	Valid
X33	0,646	0,361	Valid
X34	0,432	0,361	Valid
X35	0,444	0,361	Valid
X36	0,570	0,361	Valid
X37	0,642	0,361	Valid
X38	0,760	0,361	Valid
Purchase Decision (Y)			
Y1	0,469	0,361	Valid
Y2	0,466	0,361	Valid
Y3	0,642	0,361	Valid
Y4	0,390	0,361	Valid
Y5	0,505	0,361	Valid

Table 1 presents the results of the validity test for each statement. The results of data processing indicate that all statements are valid because the corrected item-total correlation value is higher or equal to the r-table value of 0.361.

Reliability Test

This reliability test uses SPSS application with Cronbach's Alpha higher than > 0.60 .

Reliability test results can be seen in Table 2:

Table 2: Reliability Test	
Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,929	27

Reliability Test is used to measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of the variables. The questionnaire is considered reliable if responses from respondents to inquiries are consistent from time to time.

Table 3: Multiple Linear Regression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig,
	B	Std, Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1,870	1,887		
Advertising	,073	,062	,124	1,175	,244
Personal selling	,450	,114	,472	3,945	,000
Sales promotion	,165	,081	,219	2,026	,046

Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Table 3 presents the results of data processing to determine the following multiple linear regression equation models: $1.870 = 0,073 X_1 + 0,450 X_2 + 0,165 X_3 + \varepsilon$

Hypothesis Test

Simultaneous Test Results

Table 4: Simultaneous Test Results

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig,
Regression	156,720	3	52,240	29,503	,000 ^b
Residual	136,341	77	1,771		
Total	293,062	80			

Table 4 presents the empirical results of simultaneous tests. The value of the F-count is 29,503, and a significant level is 0,000. Whereas, the F-table value at a significant level of 95% is 2.49 where (F-count > F-table) or $29,503 > 2.49$ and sig value ($0.000 < 0.05$). It means there is a significant effect of advertising (X1) Personal Selling (X2) and Sales Promotion (X3) on Purchase Decision (Y) simultaneously.

Partial Test Results

Table 5: Partial Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig,
	B	Std, Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1,870	1,887		
Advertising	,073	,062	,124	1,175	,244
Personal selling	,450	,114	,472	3,945	,000
Sales promotion	,165	,081	,219	2,026	,046

Table 5 presents partial test results as follows:

Advertising (X1)

The t-count value is 1.175, and the t-table value is 1.66. The result shows t-count value < t-table or ($1.175 < 1.66$) and sig value ($0.024 > 0.05$). It is concluded that advertising partially has an insignificant effect on the purchase decision.

Personal Selling (X2)

The t-count value is 3,945, and t-table value is 1.66. The result shows t-count value > t-table ($3,945 > 1.66$) and sig value ($0.000 < 0.05$). It is concluded that personal selling partially has a significant effect on the purchase decision.

Sales Promotion (X2)

The t-count value is 2,026, and t-table value is 1.66. Evidence shows t-count value > t-table (2,026 > 1.66) and sig value (0.046 < 0.05). It is concluded that sales promotion partially has a significant effect on the purchase decision.

Coefficient of Determination

Table 6: Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,731 ^a	,535	,517	1,33066

Table 6 presents the results of R which is 0.731 or 71.3%. The result shows that the research constructs contribute to explain the purchase decision which is 71.3% while other factors outside of this study have influenced the remaining 28.7%.

Discussion

The effect of advertising on purchase decisions

Based on the results of the study, there is a positive effect between the consumer purchase decision on the product and the advertising, although the relationship is not significant. The results of this study are supported by Ramdani's (2016) research that advertising has an insignificant effect on the purchasing decision. This work is insignificant may the research sample who used Padang cement in Medan City. Most consumers choose to buy products instead of displayed ads such as brochures or billboards.

The effect of personal selling on purchase decisions

The result of the research shows that there is a positive and significant influence between the decision of consumer purchase of Padang cement product in Medan city with personal selling. The results of this study are also supported by a study conducted by Arman (2015) which states that partially it is recognized that personal sales have a significant effect on consumer buying decisions. Personal selling has a significant influence on the purchase of Padang cement products is also influenced by the ability of salespeople to provide information and serve consumers towards the products offered. Also, personal selling can provide personal relationships between sellers and buyers. In addition to notifying product information, persuading potential buyers, personal selling is also able to accommodate complaints and suggestions from buyers to sellers so that it can be feedback for the company.

The effect of sales promotion on purchase decisions

The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between the consumer purchasing decision on the Padang cement product in Medan and the sales promotion. Supported by research conducted by Febryan, Zainul and Fransisca (2014) which states that partially it is known that sales promotion variables have a significant effect on consumer purchase decisions. In line with Hermawan (2012) who stated that sales promotion is a form of direct persuasion through the use of various incentives that can be set to stimulate the purchase of goods immediately or increase the number of consumer goods purchased. Through company sales promotions can attract new customers, encourage greater buyer

costs, attack competitors' promotion activities and increase impulsive buying PT Semen Padang conducts sales promotion activities such as giving gifts or discounts to consumers more effectively. Because of the increasing popularity of promotional activities in the form of incentives or rewards made by other competitors' cement. Consumers are currently more interested in buying products offered based on gifts provided by the company

CONCLUSIONS & SUGGESTIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, the conclusions of this study are advertising, personal selling and sales promotion simultaneously have the positive and significant effect on consumer purchase decisions of Padang cement products in Medan City. Partially, advertising has a positive and an insignificant to purchase decision. Personal selling has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. Sales promotion has a positive and significant effect on consumer decision of Padang cement product in Medan City. The personal selling is the most dominant variable affecting the consumer purchasing decision on the Padang cement product in Medan City. Salesperson's ability to provide information and persuasion to consumers greatly affect consumers in making purchasing decisions. Concerning the problems faced by PT Semen Padang, the promotion cost is increasing every year, and sales income are increasing, but it has not reached the expected demand target and the decrease of market share every year. Promotion activities conducted by PT Semen Padang in the form of advertising has not been effective and did not affect consumer purchase decisions. Based on the coefficient of determination (R test) states that the value of R is 0.731 which means that the relationship among advertising, personal selling, and sales promotion with the purchase decision is related.

Suggestions

Researchers advised that PT Semen Padang continued to conduct promotional activities such as personal selling and sales promotion because both of them had a significant influence on purchasing decisions. PT Semen Padang should provide a more insightful view of advertising because in the research conducted, and Advertising does not affect the consumer's purchasing decisions. The use of mix media by the seller to communicate persuasive information about products, services or organizations and is a powerful promotional tool such as providing brochures or advertising advertisements in print media such as newspapers or billboards as well as in electronic media such as radio or television. Also, the company should also strengthen its relationship with personal selling because based on the results of this research, the salesperson gives the most prominent role to the purchase decision of the Padang cement product. Based on product lifecycle theory, PT Semen Padang is currently in the maturity stage, an innovative strategy made by PT Semen Padang using advertisements that persuasive and influence consumers to use their products.

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